

Effect of Green Banking Practice (GBP) on Financial Performance of Quoted Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria, 2014 – 2024

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Abstract

This study investigated the effect of Green Banking Practices (GBP) on Financial Performance of Quoted Deposit Money Banks (QDMBs) in the South East Nigeria, 2014-2024. Specifically, the study examined the effect of Green Products and Services (GPS), Green Banking Strategy (GBS) and Green Investment (GIV) on the financial performance of quoted deposit money banks in South East Nigeria. The study utilized cross sectional survey research design. The population of the study consists of 550 employees and customers of quoted deposit money banks (QDMBs) listed in the Nigeria Exchange Group in the South East of Nigeria. Questionnaire was administered on 520 respondents, both employees and customers which were selected through random sampling method. Descriptive and inferential statistics were used to analyse the data at 0.05 level of significance. The study established that green banking practices have positive and significant effect on return on investment; (Adj.R2 = .520, f stat = 107.408) .000 $p < 0.05$) of quoted deposit money banks in Nigeria. It is concluded that green banking practices, green banking strategy and green investments improved financial performance of quoted deposit money banks in Nigeria within the period under review. The future of green banking seems to be very promising in Nigeria, as lots of green products and services are expected in the future. Green excellence awards and recognition, green rating agencies, green investment funds, green insurance, and green accounting and disclosure are some of the things that will be heard and seen in operations in the near future. Therefore, the study recommended that Central Bank of Nigeria should develop specific guidelines on green banking practices for the banking industry and motivate banks to adopt the practice and reporting as mainstream strategy. CBN should commit to long-term investment on green end-of-life management since it is the least employed green production practice.

Keywords: Green Banking Practice, Green Product Services, Green Banking strategy, Green Investment, Deposit Money Bank.

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Introduction

Climate change has drastically affected the world environment through excessive flooding, storms, earthquake, excessive heats and rainfall. The fear of environmental associated problems is increasing worldwide and recently, businesses and institutions, leading to the establishment of methods of managing climate problems. (Gbanador, 2016). Zheng *et al* (2022) argue that nations have implemented several policies to minimize the risks of unfavorable environmental impacts of climate change. Hossain (2018) noted that some of the major methods established to prevent the degradation of the environment include the introduction of green banking and finance, which is consistent with global best practice and promotion of sustainable economic growth and development. Sun *et al* (2020) argued that the idea of green banking and finance has encouraged banking institutions to introduce paperless, technology-based

services, and to sustain their role as a responsible entity in sustainable development while minimizing the impact on the environment. Green banking performs an essential role in the attainment of sustainable development of any given nation.

According to Hassan *et al* (2022), green banking is the investment solutions that guard the environment, provide social justice, and establish economic attainment conveying preference in the banking industry to safeguard banks and society against unforeseen and impending economic concerns such as international economic volatility, environmental alteration, public disturbance, and corporate failures. Green Banking has been identified as a veritable measure for the reduction of carbon footprints from the activities of banks as well as creating awareness and consciousness about the environment (Gbanador, 2016). The implication of green banking operation is that the environment benefits from banking since its operation is tailored in a way that it promote sustainable environment and socially responsible investments. A Deposit Money Bank can transform to a green bank by simply structuring their activities in a way that is environment friendly (Gbanador, 2016). This is because their contribution to carbon footprint is minimal compared to other sectors.

However, the reverse is the case for the activities of their clients. This necessitated the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) to issue the circular number FPR/DIR/CIR/GEN/01/33 titled “Implementation of Sustainable Banking Principles by Banks, Discount Houses and Development Institutions in Nigeria”. This circular was approved by the Bankers’ Committee, at its retreat of July 14, 2012 (CBN, 2012). The essence was to deliver positive development impacts to society while protecting the communities and environment in which financial institutions and their customers operate. Thus, banks are expected to examine and manage their activity’s risk most especially in the area of project finance. The essence is to reduce carbon footprint thereby promoting a healthy environment. One of the prominent ways of adopting green Banking is by ensuring that the products offered by the banks are environment friendly. This could be done by offering electronic banking products through the internet, mobile and paperless banking channels etc. By so doing, there will be adequate reduction in the accumulation of wastes that are harmful to the environment.

Statement of the problem

In recent years, there has been an increasing focus on green banking (GB) by financial institutions which aim to tackle environmental and social challenges without compromising profitability. GB involves integrating environmental and social considerations into banking operations and services to promote sustainable development and combat climate change.

The idea of “green banking” or “green initiatives” adopted by banks involves developing new technologies, streamlining current processes, and altering customer behavior. It entails encouraging eco-friendly behaviors and lowering the carbon footprint of financial operations. The life of every nation’s economic activities depends on the soundness of its financial sector. Where there is no conducive environment in areas of security, energy, and infrastructure for operations, sustainability will not be achieved.

Going green in the banking sector will aid in eliminating these problems. Green banking is a means of developing inclusive banking strategies which will ensure substantial economic development and promoting environmental-friendly practices and Eco-consciousness and sustainability. The problem which this study tends to address was to investigate the effect of green banking practice on financial performance of quoted deposit money banks in Nigeria.

Objectives of the study.

The main objective of the study was to investigate the effect of Green Banking Practices (GBP) on Financial Performance of quoted Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria.

The specific objectives of the study are to:

- 1) examine the impact of green product and services (GPS) on the financial performance of deposit money bank in Nigeria.
- 2) examine the relationship between green business/banking strategy (GBS) and financial performance of deposit money Banks in Nigeria.
- 3) determine the effect of Green Investment (GIN) on the performance of deposit money banks in Nigeria.

Statement of Research Hypotheses

H1: Green products and services have no positive and significant impact on performances of deposit money banks in Nigeria.

H2: Green business strategy has no causal relationship with financial performances of deposit money banks in Nigeria.

H3: Green investment has no positive and significant effect on performances of deposit money banks in Nigeria.

Review of Related Literature

Conceptual Framework

Green Banking Practices: Green banking is defined as banking practices that promotes environmentally-friendly practices and decreasing the volume of carbon footprints from the activities of banks (Appah, Tebepah and Eburunobi, 2024)

Guang-Wen and Siddik (2022), Ziolo *et al* (2019) described green banking as banking practices that protects the environment, promise collective justice, and generate economic accomplishment conveying priority in banking business to safeguard banks and society against unforeseen future economic challenges.

Green Banking is an evolving approach, which aims to address environmental concerns through the bank's functional activities to foster sustainable development in the banking industry (Pawar and Munuswamy, 2022)

Green Banking includes the judicious use of all resources and energy, reduces the carbon footprint, and encourages, finances, and educates customers on environmentally friendly investment (Jayabal and Soudarya (2017). The major handicap of the Nigeria is the mismanagement of resources, as the country is endowed with numerous resources.

Kanu, *et al* (2020) gave the following as the benefits of green banking practice;

Reduces the Transaction Costs of the Bank: Green banking avoids paperwork as much as possible and follows electronic media for various transactions, the functioning of banks, and customer management through providing e -statements to customers, opening online accounts, making all internal circulars within the banks online, etc. Thus, paperless banking reduces transaction costs.

Competitive Edge: Green banking helps banks to get a competitive edge over their competitors through innovation in their products and services.

Better Risk Management: It provides the benefit of better risk management to the banks. Better risk management helps in building a good image of the banks and therefore reducing the reputational risk.

Reduces the Credit Risk: Green banking makes recovery of the financed loans easy and thus reduces the credit risk of the bank. Green banking encourages the development of a peaceful environment.

Cost Conscious Process: The transaction costs incurred by the bank through green banking products like ATMs, mobile banking, and online banking are significantly minimized compared to the costs incurred through customers visiting the branch and performing transactions.

Convenient Process: Green Banking provides convenience to banks and also to the banks' customers. Due to various green banking initiatives like the use of ATMs, online banking, mobile banking, etc., the foot fall of the customers in the branches of the banks reduces to a larger extent, and this leads to reduced cost and effort in the management of the banks' activities. These banking activities also provide convenience to the consumers in terms of time management, energy, and fuel conservation as they do not need to visit the branch for every transaction.

Green Product and Services

Banking products can be conveniently categorized into three viz; core products, customer offerings and customer support services. Core products are the traditional financial services which Afolabi (2002), gave as five, these includes, deposit mobilization, credit and loan, funds transmission, foreign exchange and general and financial advisory services. They together form the bedrock of bank services. Customer offerings are set of products fashioned out of traditional core products in order to suit the purposes and meet peculiar needs of different customers. Thus, from deposit mobilization is fashioned out target savings such as Higher Institution Fund Account, Christmas, Hadj and Ileya savings account. While from credit and loan services is fashioned out Housing Loan, Asset Acquisition Loans etc. Customer support services are another set of products also fashioned out of core products made possible with the level of available technology with the aim of making services more suitable and conducive to customers to customers.

Abiodun, Iyobhebhe and Okundalaiye (2024) described Green Product as products whose manufacturing and production are eco-friendly and have minimal damaging effect to the environment. This means that the raw materials, input items, processes and developments of such products are based on resources that can be preserved and recycled. Purwanti *et al* (2019) stated that green products are ecological products that put priority on the long-term safety of user and the environment, green products are made through not wasting resources and do not involve cruelty to man or animal kind. Additionally, green product quality is measured based on the reflection of environmental features on the product (Abiodun, Iyobhebhe and Okundalaiye, 2024).

This is because consumers decisions are influenced by the knowledge of green product qualities such as non-polluting materials, recyclability, high level energy saving and assurance of minimal negative impact in the environment (Gelderman *et al.*, 2021). This argument is similarly put forward by Silaban *et al* (2021) in terms of the fact that green products should not harm humans or the environment in any way. A green product is a sustainable product designed to minimize environmental impacts during its whole life-cycle and even after it's of no use.

Green products are usually identified by having two basic goals – reducing waste and maximizing resource efficiency. Green car loans, energy efficiency mortgages, alternative energy venture capital, eco-savings deposits, and “green” credit cards; these items represent merely a handful of innovative, “green” financial products that are currently offered around the globe. In an age where environmental risks and opportunities abound, so too have the options for reconciling environmental matters with lending and financing arrangements. (UNEP, 2024)

Green Business/ Banking Strategy:

Yousaf *et al.* (2021) defines green business/Banking strategy (GBS) as a considerable and robust organizational propensity to include environmental concerns in the business plans of all organizational

departments. Organizations that engage in environmentally responsible practices generate a variety of opportunities. As a result, enterprises receive various benefits and satisfy numerous stakeholders' needs. Several studies have demonstrated that green business methods boost firms' earnings and performance. Multiple levels of advocacy for environmental protection. Numerous production aspects have an impact on the environment, particularly materials. The operational principles focus on the actual, day-to-day aspects of running a sustainable business, whilst the strategic principles are utilized largely to determine the business direction (Soderholm, 2020)

Green Investment:

Green investment refers to investments that aim to mitigate the negative effects of human activities on the environment and promote the shift toward a sustainable, low carbon, and resource-efficient economy using a type of able energy, energy efficiency, and sustainable transportation (Judith *et al* (2020). As climate change and sustainable development gain more attention, green investment is becoming increasingly important. Green investment is a crucial element in the pursuit of a sustainable and low-carbon economy, offering significant potential for environmental, social, and economic benefits. The investment in renewable power capacity surpassed that of fossil fuel-fired power capacity, highlighting the growing trend towards green investment and its potential to drive the transition towards a low carbon economy (Suo, *et al*, 2021). Green investment not only has the potential to reduce greenhouse gas emissions and other environmental impacts but also to stimulate economic growth, create new jobs, and enhance human well-being (UNEP, 2021)

“Green investment” refers to using public and private funds to purchase products and services that benefit the environment, such as preserving ecosystem diversity and repairing climate harm (Tran, *et al*, 2020). This investment serves society’s three primary duties of preserving the environment, conserving resources, and upholding fairness and justice (Rokhmawati, 2021). It is also morally right and consistent with an ecological civilization. The objective of a circular economy also incorporates green investment. It combines and coordinates the benefits of the economy, environment, and society to accomplish long-term social and economic development and create a harmonious society.

Performance Measures of Banks

Measuring bank financial performance is a bit like measuring the performance of a traditional company. In their view, eHow (2012), posit that business revenue is the returns made from investments, and this income comes from interest or asset appreciation on investments. Banks, he argued, must also consider the cost of funds used to make these investments.

The capacity to generate sustainable profitability is usually used to determine bank’s performance. Profitability is essential for a bank to maintain organization activities and for its investment to generate fair returns.

ECB (2011), established that the main drivers of bank’s profits are; earnings, efficiency, risk-taking and leverage. They claimed that the large set of bank performance measures usually employed by academics, researchers and practitioners alike include traditional, economic and market-based while traditional measures are similar to those applied in other industries with ROA (returns on assets), ROE (returns on equity), and Cost-to-income being the most widely used. And given the importance of the inter mediation function of banks, net interest margin is also considered. ECB, (2011).

Conceptual Framework Model

Conceptual framework to measure effect of green banking and financial performance of commercial banks

Green Product and Services: These refer to banking products and services that are environmentally friendly and promote sustainability. They may include eco-friendly loans, green energy financing, and sustainable investment options

Green Investment: This variable pertains to investments made by banks in environmentally sustainable projects and initiatives, such as renewable energy projects, green infrastructure, and carbon reduction initiatives. (Jayabal & Soundarya, 2016)

Green Banking Strategies: These encompass the policies, practices, and approaches adopted by banks to integrate environmental considerations into their operations and decision-making processes. It involves initiatives like reducing carbon emissions, promoting recycling, and supporting environmental conservation efforts. (Salvadó *et al.*, 2013)

Financial Performance: This variable represents the subjective evaluation of a bank's financial performance by stakeholders, including customers, investors, and regulators. It encompasses perceptions of efficiency, effectiveness, and economy in relation to green banking practices. (Biswakarma, 2017; Risal & Joshi, 2018)

Theoretical Framework

This study was guided by Environmental Interest Theory propounded by Shaumya and Arulrajah in 2017. This theory suggests that the emergence of green banking practices stems from a genuine concern for environmental sustainability and a desire to mitigate the ecological footprint of financial institutions. Advocates of this theory argue that banks recognize their role in environmental stewardship and aim to proactively address environmental challenges through the adoption of environmentally friendly policies and practices. By integrating sustainability principles into their operations, banks seek to contribute positively to environmental conservation efforts while also enhancing their reputation as socially responsible institutions (Shaumya & Arulrajah, 2017)

Empirical Review

Gbanador and Okeke (2023) examined the effect of green banking practice on the performance of Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria. The study employed the historical data research design while the quarterly time series data spanning through the period of 2012 to 2021 were collated from the CBN Statistical Bulletin. The Johansen cointegration test, Parsimonious Error Correction model and the fully modified Least Square were used for the data analysis. The findings indicated evidence of long-run relationship between green banking and the performance of Deposit money banks. Thus, the study concludes that banks can enhance their performance and environmental protection by adopting and promoting socially responsible and environmentally sustainable investment through the vehicle of green banking. In view of the findings therefore, the researcher suggests that the Central Bank of Nigeria should formulate and implement relevant policies that will encourage the full adoption of green banking practices by banks. Finally, Deposit Money Banks should educate their customers as well as creating awareness regarding the benefit of utilizing the electronic banking products in order to enhance the adoption of green banking in Nigeria.

Tandukar *et al.* (2021) examined the popularity of going green in the banking and finance sectors and explore factors influencing bankers' perceptions of green banking success. Conventional sampling methods gathered data from 326 financial representatives through surveys between June and October. Findings revealed limited awareness of green banking practices among only 5% of respondents, highlighted the need for training and improved online customer support in banks. The study emphasized the importance of raising awareness to promote sustainable and environmentally responsible banking practices.

Enyi, Adebajo and Adudu (2024) investigated the effect of green production on the performance of small and medium enterprises in North Central Nigeria. Specifically, the study examined the effect of green products, green processes and operations, green use and green end-of-life management on the performance of small and medium enterprises in North Central Nigeria. The study is anchored on Ecological Modernization Theory and Stakeholders Theory. This study utilized the survey research design, the study area is North Central Nigeria, comprising of Benue State, Kogi State, Kwara State, Nasarawa State, Niger State, Plateau State and the Federal Capital Territory. The population of the study was 1,784 with a sample size of 327 generated scientifically using Yamén's Formula.

The study established that there are positive relationships between the dimensions of green production and performance of Agro-processing small businesses in Nigeria. It is concluded that green production through green products, green processes and operations, green use and green end-of-life management can improve the performance of small and medium enterprises in North Central, Nigeria

Ma.Monica *et al* (2024) analyzes how green business strategy (GBS) and corporate social responsibility (CSR) impact financial performance (FP). The empirical application uses structural equation modeling on a sample of 300 manufacturing firms from Mexico. The results show positive and significant relationships between GBS, CSR and FP, while the significantly positive mediating role of CSR was also verified.

Abiodun, Iyobhebhe and Okundal (2023) investigated the effect of green marketing strategies on consumer purchasing decision in the fast-moving-consumer-goods (FMCG) industry in Nigeria based on insights gathered from consumers in selected areas of Lagos State. The study adopted a quantitative research approach based on survey research design to gather primary data from a sample of 400 respondents selected via judgmental and convenience sampling technique. The data was collected through a structured questionnaire and was analysed using descriptive statistics. The results of data analysis indicated that consumers do not experience cognitive dissonance/dissatisfaction with green FMCG products of their preferred organization.

Jianmu and Efifania (2024) looked at the effect of green financing and investment on the performance of deposit money bank. The study used quantitative research techniques through primary and secondary data sources from Indonesia's 238 sampled international chemical companies. Additionally, a standardized questionnaire was employed in this study to gather data. The study used Smart-PLS and a structural equation model (SEM) to examine the data gathered and determine the relationship between green investment, green financing, CSR, and sustainable business performance. The study shows that green investments and financing significantly and favorably affect CSR and sustainable performance.

Methodology

Research Design:

Cross sectional survey research design was used to investigate the effect of green banking practices on financial performance of quoted deposit money banks in Nigeria with emphasis on the South East zone of Nigeria, 2014-2024. This method of research design was adopted because it systematically collects, analyse and synthesize quantitative data on a large representative sample of a given population to describe and explain the relative incidence, distribution and interrelations of variables (Appah, 2020).

The population of the study consists of 550 respondents both staff and customers of quoted deposit money banks (QDMBs) listed in the Nigeria Exchange Group in the South East of Nigeria. The accessible population consisted of the following banks branches customers and staff. (First Bank, Union Bank, Access Bank, Fidelity Bank, United Bank for Africa, Guaranty Trust Bank, Zenith Bank, Ecobank, First City Monument Bank) in Abia, Anambra, Ebonyi, Enugu, Imo states of Nigeria.

The study adopted stratified random sampling technique and a sample size of five hundred and twenty (520) questionnaires were used for the study. The data for this study were collected using well structured questionnaire titled “Green Banking Practices on Financial Performance of deposit money Banks in Nigeria. The independent variable of green banking practices was measured using Green Bank Practice and services, Green Banking/business strategy and Green Investment while the dependent variable was measured using banks Return on Investment (ROI). The questionnaire was validated using content validity and Cronbach Alpha (α) was used to ascertain the statistical reliability of the research instrument with a good degree of reliability at 0.92. The questionnaire administered to the respective respondents were also analysed with a three (3) distinct stages of data analysis using univariate analysis (descriptive statistics), bivariate analysis (correlation matrix) and multivariate analysis (multiple regression) which involves the independent variables, green bank practices proxy by green product and services, green business strategy and green investment and the dependent variable bank performance, proxy by Return on Investment (ROI).

Model specification

The model specified to test the hypothesis of this study is formulated as follows:

$$ROI = f(GPS, GBS, GIN)$$

Where

- ROI = Return on Investment,
- GPS = Green Product Services,
- GBS = Green Banking Strategy
- GIN= Green Investment

The regression model, thus is given as

$$ROI = x + \beta_1 GPS + \beta_2 GBS + \beta_3 GIN + e \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

Where x = Intercept of the regression $\beta_1 - \beta_4$ = parameter estimates

e = error term

Data Presentation

In order to have the 550 return rate of the questionnaire distributed to respondents in the deposit money bank chosen for this study, out of which five hundred and twenty seven (520), were successfully filled and returned in analyzable form, recording a 97.0 % return rate.

Descriptive Statistics Analysis

The result in Table 1 shows predictors of the dependent and independent variables. The mean and standard deviation show the level of agreement of the respondents with the questions. For green product Services it has the mean and standard deviation values as (M=5.53, SD=0.720); green banking strategy has mean value of 5.62 and standard deviation =0.630; green investment has (M=5.52, SD=0.726);

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics Analysis

Variable	Mean	Standard Deviation
Green Product Services	5.53	.720
Green Banking Strategy	5.62	.630
Green Investment	5.52	.726

Source: Authors computation from SPSS Output, 2024

Regression Analysis

The model used to test the hypotheses designed for this study, exploring the effect of green product practice on the performance of deposit money banks in Nigeria is multiple regression.

The result of the model summary in Table 2 explains the relationship between the dependent variable and the independent variables and the goodness of fit in the model in terms of R-value and R square. The R² value of 0.678 entails that 67.8% of bank financial performance was explained by predictor variables which include green product and services, green banking strategy, green investment. The remaining 32.2% is explained by other factors not included in this study. The value of R (.860) indicates that there is a strong relationship between the variables.

Table 2: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adj.R Square	Std. Error of estimation	Durbin watson
1	.860 ^a	.678	.520	.451	1.832

a: Predictors (constant), Green Product Services, Green Banking Strategy, Green Investment

b. Dependent variable: Return on Investment (ROI)

Source: SPSS printout (Version 25.0 for windows output), 2024

The result of the Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) in Table 3 describes the effect of the independent variables on the dependent variable since the F value was more than 4 and significance level is less than 0.05 (F = 107.408; Sig=0.000).

Table 3: ANOVA^b for the overall significance of the model

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean square	F	Sig
Regression	355.460	4	63.865	107.408	.000 ^b
Residual	190.867	321	0.5946		
Total	446.327	325			

a: Predictors (constant), green product services, green banking strategy, green investment

b. Dependent variable: Return on Investment (ROI)

Source: SPSS printout (Version 25.0 for windows output), 2024

The result presented in Table 4 shows that taking all other independent variables at zero, a unit change in green product services would lead to a 21.0% increase on return on investment; a unit increase green banking strategy would lead to 55.8 % change on return on Investment. Furthermore, a unit change in green investment would affect return on investment of deposit money banks performance by 18.5%. The result implies that green investment has significant effect on the return on investment of deposit money banks in Nigeria.

Table 4: Regression Coefficient Result

Model	Beta	t	Sig
1 (Constant)	1.099	1.181	.000
Green product Services	.200	3.377	.001
Green Banking Strategy	.458	8.159	.020
Green Investment	.185	1.489	.000

Dependent variable: ROI

Source: SPSS regression print out (version 25.0 for windows output), 2024.

Test of Hypotheses and Discussion of Findings

Hypothesis one: states that green product services have no significant effect on return on investment of deposit money banks in Nigeria. Regression analysis was used in testing the hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance and the significance level was less than 0.05 ($\beta = .200$; $p = .001$), hence the null hypothesis was rejected and we conclude that green product services have no significant effect on the return on investment of deposit money banks in Nigeria. The findings of this study are in agreement with that of Lin (2013), that green product innovation protects the natural environment and makes contributions to environmental benefits more than competitive products. Since, environmental concerns have become more important in the business world, green product innovation has been crucial among manufacturing companies. Many companies make investments in sustainability initiatives for risk mitigation, cost savings, and revenue generation (Dangelico *et al.*, 2017).

The result of the second hypothesis indicates that there is significant effect of green business/banking strategy on the return on investment of deposit money banks in South East Nigeria. ($\beta = .458$; $p = .020$), hence the null hypotheses which states that green business strategy has no significant effect on return on investment of deposit money banks in South East Nigeria was rejected. The findings of this study is in tandem with that of Dai and Zhang (2017), whose study revealed that green process innovation focuses on processes for saving energy during manufacturing and other processes. The findings also corroborated that of Karabulut (2019), who posit that green process innovation highlights ability of companies to enhance current processes and develop new processes for saving energy, preventing pollution, leaving less toxicity and recycling waste in innovation processes.

Hypothesis three test whether there is a significant effect on green investment on return on investment of deposit money banks in South East Nigeria and the result was as follows: $\beta = .185$; $p = .000$, hence the null hypothesis was accepted. This implies that green investment has a significant effect on the return on investment of deposit money banks in South East Nigeria. The findings are in line with Seliger, Kim *et al.* (2008), whose study found that, green use helps in minimizing emissions, waste and energy consumption associated with the product in use. This is usually achieved by changing the design of the product and implementing innovative technologies, as in the case of low-emission diesel vehicles or of the hybrid petrol electric cars released by Toyota, Nissan and Lexus (Dills & Stone, 2007; Jovane *et al.*, 2008).

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, it is concluded that the use of green products and services, green banking and strategy, green investment has improved the performance of deposit money banks in Nigeria and deposit money banks will gain competitive advantage when they implement green product since it leads to quality improvement, increased flexibility and speed.

Nigeria's economy is an emerging economy, and there is a huge potential for the growth of banks by the adoption of innovative approaches in their decision-making process. There is a need for a paradigm shift by setting up a business model that considers all three aspects of the triple bottom line approach, i.e., the people, the planet, and the profit.

The future of green banking seems to be very promising in Nigeria, as lots of green products and services are expected in the future. Green excellence awards and recognition, Green rating agencies, Green investment funds, Green insurance, and Green accounting and disclosure are some of the things that will be heard and seen in operations in the near future.

Proper green banking implementation will act as a check to the polluting industries. Banks can act like a guideline to economic transformation and create a platform that creates many opportunities for financing and investment policy and contributes towards the creation of a low-carbon economy.

Recommendations

- i. Central Bank of Nigeria should develop specific guidelines on green banking practices for the banking industry and motivate banks to adopt the practices and reporting as mainstream strategy
- ii. As the world is witnessing a big shift towards Eco-consciousness and sustainability, Stake holders in banking sector should implement green banking strategy in the operations of their banks since it highlights ability of banks to enhance current processes and develop new processes for saving energy, preventing pollution, leaving less toxicity and recycling waste in innovation processes so as to enhance their performance through market share and customer satisfaction.
- iii. CBN should commit to long-term investment on green end-of-life management since it is the least employed green production practice. This can be done if the government and other regulating institutions should come up with policies that encourage deposit money banks customers to implement green end of-life management practice.

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